

Fish market survey and Strategies of Nashik city, Maharashtra (India)

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Abstract

The study was carried out to find the status of fish availability of wholesale and Local fish market in Nashik City. Large number of Intermediaries are involved in various activities of fish selling and their distribution in city. We collected data in the month of July 2025 to December 2025 about Fishes availability and Selling Strategies in Wadalagaon, Gandhinagar, Lekhanagar, Phule Market (Bhadrakali) and Trimurti Chowk in Nashik City. This data was collected by the survey and questionnaires method. We observed total no. of 24 species of fish included the 11 fishes are freshwater, 9 species are marine water whereas 4 species are included in both marine and freshwater bodies.

Keywords: Survey, Nashik city, marine, freshwater bodies.

Introduction

Fishes are Aquatic Animal and good sources of protein, vitamins, mineral and oil. In India, fisheries contribute significantly to food security, employment and trade. Nashik city, though a non-coastal district of Maharashtra, has a rising demand for fish. Due to changing food habits, urbanization and population growth. Fish markets in Nashik act as important centers where both freshwater and marine fish are sold. The freshwater fishes are mainly sourced from nearby rivers such as Godavari, Kadwa, Darna, Vaitarna, as well as from aquaculture farms. Marine fishes are transported from coastal states like Maharashtra (Mumbai, Ratnagiri, Kolkata) and Gujarat. The study of fish markets in Nashik city is essential to understand consumer preferences, income of fish vendors, and issues related to market structure and hygiene.

Methodology

Study Area:

Fish market located in Nashik city- Wadala Gaon, Gandhi Nagar, Lekha Nagar, Phule Market (Bhadrakali) & Trimurti Chowk.

Data Collection:

The data was collected through survey of fish market with the help of observation, questionnaire and interview technique, and collecting photographs of fish with date wise and location wise. The Data were collected for a period from July 2025 to December 2025.

Photo Plate No.1: fish is available in local fish market of Nashik City.

Result and discussion

Fish like Catla, Labeo, Vam (Black & Yellow), Common Carp, Bombil, Dok are sold in large quantities as compared To Other Carps in Nashik City. Depends On Fresh Fish Available in Market in the month of October to last December the prize of fish is slightly stable in market as compared to June to September.

Table No.1: Show the fish commonly available in local fish market of Nashik City.

Common Name of Fish	Scientific Name of Fish	Rate Per Kg. (In Rupees)
Aher	<i>Anguilla bengalensis</i>	350-400
Amlī	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	200-400
Bangda / kombada / malwani bagda	<i>Rastrelliger kanagurta</i>	300-350
Bombil	<i>Harpadon nehereus</i>	120-200
Catla	<i>Catla catla</i>	250-300
Chand paplet / paplet	<i>Pampus argenteus</i>	800-1000
Chilapi	<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i> <i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	300-380
Chopda / pankaj	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i> <i>Pangasianodon hypophthalmus</i>	250-450
Dok	<i>Drepane punctata</i>	250-400
Doma	<i>Protonibea diacanthus</i>	200-300
Falai	<i>Notopterus notopterus</i>	320-380
Surmai	<i>Scomberomorus</i> spp.	1100-1200
Glass halwa	<i>Parastromateus niger</i>	350-400
Hara kata	<i>Erethistes hara</i>	300-340
Hilsa / pala masa / ilish	<i>Tenualosa ilisha</i>	800-1000
Kolambi / prwans / zinga	<i>Penaeus indicus /</i>	400-800

	<i>Penaeus monodon</i> / <i>Macrobrachium rosenbergii</i>	
Murrel	<i>Channa striata</i>	650-700
Padin	<i>Pangasius pangasius</i>	200-300
Rani fish	<i>Nemipterus japonicus</i>	320-250
Rawas	<i>Polynemus tetradactylus</i>	400-500
Rohu	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	200-400
Shingti / singata	<i>Sperata seenghala</i>	160-180
Tuna	<i>Thunnus albacares</i> <i>Thunnus obesus</i>	220-260
Vaam (black /yellow)	<i>Anguilla bengalensis</i>	800-1200

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